

On the Orientation of Signal Excitation for Magnetically Coupled Human Body Communication

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Abstract—Human body communication (HBC) technologies have vast potential in the healthcare landscape. This work focuses on Magnetic Human Body Communication (MHBC), supporting for the first time that this technique is more efficient when planar inductors are used as transceivers. A systematic study was performed to establish the most appropriate way to excite the signal into the human body to improve the channel usability and provide a design criterium for transceiver designers. Furthermore, a physical-based model is proposed and tested against channel measurements, obtaining excellent experiment-model correlation at frequencies up to 20 MHz.

Index Terms—Human body communication (HBC); magnetically-coupled HBC; Signal excitation for MHBC.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Healthcare landscape has grown significantly due to the advancement of wearable, implantable, injectable, and ingestible biomedical devices. In turn, the interconnection of those devices needs to guarantee energy efficiency and secure data transmission. To reach those requirements satisfactorily, human body communication technology (HBC) is one of the most promising proposes for wireless connectivity of sensor nodes in- and/or on-a person's body. Thus, e-health applications, such as computer-assisted rehabilitation, emergency notification, wearable ECG, or early detection of medical issues will be highly improved using HBC technologies [1]–[3].

HBC allows devices to communicate through the body tissues; therefore, the connection among them becomes intuitive since data communication can be accomplished by simply touching the devices or attaching them to the human body [4]. Currently, there are three different ways to couple the signal into the body. The first option is known as galvanic coupling (GHBC) [5], the second one is capacitive coupling (CHBC) [6], and the last one is magnetic coupling (MHBC) [7].

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As shown in Fig. 1 (a), in GHBC the signal is applied differentially using two pairs of electrodes in contact with the skin. Using this electrode configuration, the stimulated signal is maintained within the body, making this method independent of the surrounding environment [8]. Fig. 1(b) shows the CHBC method. In this case, both T_X and R_X signal electrodes are attached to the skin while ground electrodes are kept floating. Thus, this electrode configuration allows to stimulate the signal into the body and creates a return path through the air [9].

Fig. 1. Electro-Quasistatic approaches: a) Galvanic HBC and b) Capacitive HBC.

On the other hand, MHBC is implemented using two inductors, which can be: *i*) wrapped around anatomy or *ii*) placed on the skin, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Magneto-Quasistatic approach implemented using a) solenoids and b) planar coils.

The signal and ground planes are connected through a coil in both cases. Consequently, MHBC is less affected by the surrounding environment since magnetic fields can be sensed without a reference. Also, in contrast with CHBC and GHBC, MHBC doesn't require direct contact with the skin by touching

the excitation electrodes, being most robust to changes in the contact impedance, e.g., humidity by sweating [8], [10].

However, MHBC signal quality depends on the orientation of the exciting magnetic field, which is directly related to the type of inductors. Therefore, to maximize the efficiency in the design stage, this paper analyses the coupling factor over different channel distances and establishes, for the first time, a relation between the field's orientation with the channel performance for MHBC. Also, the components that describe the transmission for the MHBC system were validated using an equivalent circuit model, which provides a good model-experiment correlation up to 20 MHz and channel length up to 80 cm.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In Section II, the fundamentals of the MHBC technique when different types of inductors are used as transceivers. In sections III and IV, design considerations and coupling factor analysis are presented, Section V presents the equivalent circuit model and experimental validation, and Section VI presents the potential for practical application development using MHBC.

II. ELECTROMAGNETIC INTERACTIONS WITH TISSUES FOR MHBC

Compared to the materials typically used for implementing circuits and systems, the human body is constituted of many structures interacting simultaneously, each of which has specific properties. The main dielectric properties, such as permittivity and conductivity, are highly frequency dependent [11], as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Relative permittivity (ϵ_r) and conductivity (σ) of muscle, skin, blood, and fat. Data was taken from Gabriel's works [11].

Usually, the relative permeability (μ_r) is taken as 1 for human body tissues, so the human body becomes transparent to magneto-quasistatic fields. Nevertheless, the structure and composition of biological tissues consist of complex physical subsystems, including ions, polar molecules such as water, proteins, lipids, hormones, colloidal particles, and others. Some of them have a magnetic behavior; therefore, the total induced current density (\mathbf{J}) in the body must be expressed by the superposition of the drift, diffusion, and polarization currents of those charged elements. In this regard, the frequency-domain Ampere's law gives the ratio between drift and displacement current densities by the ratio $\omega\epsilon/\sigma$ [12]. As shown in Fig. 4, this ratio depends on the tissue's cellular structure, frequency of excitation, and electromagnetic properties.

Fig. 4. Ratio $\omega\epsilon/\sigma$ for muscle, skin, blood, and fat [12].

Then, the total current flowing through and along with cells, membranes, and cellular fluids can follow different pathways, as illustrated in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of tissues and electrical current flow.

In order to get an electrical interpretation of the HBC channel, a parallel equivalent circuit of capacitive and conductive elements has been proposed in [13]. As shown in Fig. 6 (a), this equivalent circuit considers the extracellular fluid resistance (R_e), the parallel capacitance of the extracellular fluid (C_e), the resistance and capacitance of the cell membrane (R_m and C_m), and the resistance and capacitance of the intracellular fluid (R_i and C_i). The equivalent circuit can be simplified for intermediate frequencies, as shown in Fig. 6 (b). Nevertheless, to get complete modeling of the HBC channel, non-linear conductance and inductive effects (L_e) are included in a conventional model [14], [15], as shown in Fig. 6(c).

Fig. 6. (a) Equivalent circuit of a cell, (b) Simplified model of a cell, and (c) model including induced currents.

In particular, non-linear inductive effects seem to be associated with the time delay for the onset of the K^+ and Na^+ currents under excitation in a typical excitable membrane, also cell torques and current loops associated with diffusion gradients in the cellular fluids [14], [15]. Thus, both transversal and longitudinal effects must be considered in the model for the HBC channel interpretation, as illustrated in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Equivalent circuit model for human tissues showing transversal and longitudinal current paths.

R_L , R_T , R_{Ti} , R_{Li} , L_L , L_T , C_L , and C_T represent the effective resistive, inductive, and capacitive effects given for longitudinal and transversal currents in intra/extracellular paths.

In the case of the MHBC technique, the orientation of the magnetic field (B) generated in the transmitter plays an important role in the signal stimulation into the body. As shown in Fig. 8, the B -field, generated by the current I_{TX} on the transmitter side, induces an electric field (E) inside the body. If a solenoid inductor is used as a transmitter, the induced E -field oscillates perpendicularly to the receiver location. This case is illustrated in Fig. 8(a) and is named *transversal*. On the other hand, if a planar inductor is used as a transmitter, the E -field oscillates in the same direction as the receiver inductor is placed. This case is illustrated in Fig. 8(b) and is named *longitudinal*.

Fig. 8. Field interactions of the body with: (a) TX/RX solenoids and (b) TX/RX planar inductors.

Then, a B field oscillating in the z -direction increases the current density in the x - y plane, as illustrated in Fig. 8(a). Likewise, a B field oscillating in the y -direction increases the current density in the x - z plane, as illustrated in Fig. 8(b). Therefore, an increment in the current density in the longitudinal direction (or x - z plane) favors the coupling of the in-body signal with the receiver, which may be evidenced by an increment in the magnetic coupling coefficient (k).

When TX and RX coils are coupled through the body, each has a separate coupling coefficient. Then, two coupling-ratio factors are defined as [16]–[18]:

$$kb_{TX} = \Phi_{TR} / \Phi_{TX} \quad (1)$$

$$kb_{RX} = \Phi_{RT} / \Phi_{RX} \quad (2)$$

The coupling ratio kb_{TX} , defines the fraction of the flux of the TX coil (Φ_{TX}) linking the RX coil through the body. Similarly, kb_{RX} determines the portion of the flux of the RX (Φ_{RX}) coil linking the TX coil. Φ_{TR} and Φ_{RT} represent the part of the flux that induces an electromotive force (*emf*) in the receiver or in the transmitter coil, respectively.

The coupling coefficient is widely used when referring to magnetically coupled systems, and for non-linear systems can be expressed as [16]–[18]:

$$kb_{TX}kb_{RX} = M_{TR}M_{RT} / L_{TX}L_{RX} \quad (3)$$

Where L_{TX} and L_{RX} represent the TX and RX self-inductances, while M_{TR} and M_{RT} represent the mutual inductances when the TX-coil is coupled to the RX-coil through the body and vice versa.

According to (1)–(3), coupling between transmitter and receiver coils depends on the amount of Φ linking them through the body. Thus, in the design stage for MHBC transceivers, coil geometry, their orientation with respect to the body, and the closeness of the TX and the RX coils must be considered for practical application scenarios.

To validate the crucial role of the coil's orientation in the accurate characterization of the MHBC channel. The human body channel for MHBC was explored by EM simulations in HFSS. In this case, the detailed HFSS human model was used to implement different scenarios. As shown in Fig. 9, solenoids were used to stimulate the E -field in the body considering three setups: the first one uses the solenoids wrap-around the arm, shown in Fig. 9 (a); the second setup is shown in Fig. 9 (b), where the solenoids are used close on the body; and finally, a set of planar coils were used as shown in Fig. 9 (c).

Fig. 9. EM simulations for MHBC using (a) solenoids in transversal orientation; (b) solenoids in longitudinal orientation; (c) planar inductor; and (d) the corresponding pathloss results.

The simulation results for the pathloss are shown in Fig. 9 (d). Notice that the transmission level is higher when the inductors are placed to induce an E-field in the longitudinal direction, evidencing that this orientation of excitation favored the signal transmission between transmitter and receiver.

Fig. 9 (d) shows a comparison when the planar or the solenoid coil is oriented longitudinally. In this case, the induced E-field is in the same direction, favoring the transmission between the TX and RX; however, planar inductors improve the signal excitation. It could be associated with the fact that in planar coils are lower turn number and wider spacing (or smaller facing area) of each turn reduces the parasitic capacitance and the proximity effect, improving the signal coupling. In addition, the planar inductor expands the effective area over the skin, increasing the electro-quasistatic (EQS) near field coupling and consequently bringing a better coupling with the HBC channel.

The HBC channel is composed of intrinsic and extrinsic paths [6]. For MHBC, the extrinsic path is related to the inductor's coupling through the air. This coupling depends on the geometry and proximity of the TX and RX. The following section presents design considerations to establish the geometrical parameters of coils; also, the coupling path through the air is experimentally obtained.

III. INDUCTOR DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS

The electrode design for HBC systems is a challenging issue due, among others, to the randomness of users. Thus, to perform measurements and compare the different cases mentioned in the previous section, it is necessary to consider the physical limitations of implementing MHBC systems.

Until now, no criteria have been applied to select an adequate diameter for the wire-wound excitation. For that reason, this paper proposes to start with the basic restrictions established by the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) [19] regarding the maximum possible exposure (MPE) and non-ionizing radiation limits of the human body to time-varying electric, and magnetic fields. Depending on the frequency of the field, different physical quantities are used to set the restriction of exposure. For frequencies in the 1 Hz -100 MHz range, *current density* (J) provides the restriction to prevent effects on the central nervous system. In the 100 MHz -10 GHz range, restrictions are provided on *Specific energy Absorption Rate* (SAR) to prevent heat stress on the body. Also, power density is restricted between the 10 GHz – 300 GHz frequency range to prevent heating in body tissue or near the skin surface [20]. Under these first considerations, a frequency from 1 to 20 MHz was established to perform secure measurements, seeing that the induced current density limit for this range is $J=20$ mA/cm² [19].

Once the value for J was defined, it is possible to apply a simple circular conductive loop model to approximate the induced currents in different organs and body regions, e.g., arms, by using the following equation derived from Faraday's law of induction:

$$J = \pi R f \sigma B \quad (4)$$

Where B is the magnetic flux density and R is the radius of the loop coil for induction of the current.

Then, to establish the self-inductance value for transmitter and receiver inductors, it is necessary to define a coil diameter. Since MHBC is a technique mainly focused on developing wearable technologies, it is very helpful to consider the anthropometric media dimensions of the human body, which are provided by the international standard ISO7250-1 (Basic Human Body Measurements for Technological Design) [21]. According to the databases based on ISO7250-1, the mean value for human forearm circumference is 310 mm for males and 264 mm for females [22], [23]. Thus, the approximate diameter for the TX/RX coil must be between 80 to 100 mm.

Using (4) and including a homogeneous conductivity for the body of 0.5 Sm^{-1} [11] leads to determining from (5) that a 1 μH coil is required.

$$L = J / \pi R f \sigma I_{TX} \quad (5)$$

Once the inductive value of the TX/RX coils was determined, two equivalent inductor sets were fabricated to implement the MHBC test setup. The solenoids were fabricated with 2.5 turns spaced 10 mm, as shown in Fig. 10 a). As well, the equivalent planar square coils with 67.3 mm of the side were fabricated using an FR4 substrate with a thickness of 1.6 mm; the copper trace has a width of 2 mm and 1.5 mm of trace spacing, as shown in Fig. 10 b). Here its important to remark that this methodology can be extrapolate for other coil sizes; however, safety limits must be carefully observed, especially the current density limits established for this frequency range, due that in small sizes could concentrate currents could be left to heating in the skin [24].

Once the geometrical parameters were established, the inductive behavior of each coil was validated by a full-wave simulation using High Frequency Structure Simulator (HFSS) [25]. The simulation structure and its corresponding fabricated inductors are shown in Fig. 10(a) and (b) for solenoid and planar inductors, respectively.

Fig. 10. 3D model and fabricated a) solenoids and b) planar inductors.

Additionally, to validate the HFSS simulation results, one port S-parameter measurements for each coil were performed using an Anritsu Vector Network Analyzer (VNA). The equipment was previously calibrated using an SOL (short-open-load) calibration procedure, establishing a reference impedance of 50Ω .

As shown in Fig. 11, the relative difference between planar and solenoid coils is about $0.05 \mu\text{H}$, giving a good equivalence between planar and solenoid coils. Also, the experimental data well correlates with simulated results, validating the accuracy of the proposed methodology for MHBC inductor design.

Fig. 11. Electromagnetic simulation vs. experimental data for planar and solenoid inductors.

Once those inductors are appropriately designed and characterized separately, their coupling with the human body must be analyzed; this is boarded in the following sections.

IV. DETERMINATION OF THE MHBC COUPLING FACTOR

As illustrated in Fig. 12 a), the coupling between two inductors can be described by their mutual inductance and coupling factor. Frequently, T-model is used to define these parameters from experimental measurements. In accordance with the model shown in Fig. 12 b), the magnetic coupling can be defined by its corresponding impedance parameters as [26]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_1 \\ V_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Z_{11} & Z_{12} \\ Z_{21} & Z_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I_1 \\ I_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

Each parameter in the Z-matrix can be determined from the corresponding transformation of the measured S-parameters.

Each parameter of the model shown in Fig. 12 b) can be obtained from (6) as [26]:

$$Z_{11} = R_{L1} + j\omega L_1 \quad (7)$$

$$Z_{22} = R_{L2} + j\omega L_2 \quad (8)$$

$$Z_{21} = j\omega M_{12} M_{21} = j\omega (k_{12} k_{21}) (L_1 L_2) \quad (9)$$

Notice that equation (9) is in accordance with the non-linear

Fig. 12 a) Two Mutually coupled inductors and b) their equivalent T-equivalent circuit.

system expressed by (3). From (7) and (8), L_1 , L_2 , R_{L1} , and R_{L2} can be determined by:

$$L_1 = \frac{1}{\omega} \text{imag}(Z_{11}), \quad R_{L1} = \text{real}(Z_{11}) \quad (10)$$

$$L_2 = \frac{1}{\omega} \text{imag}(Z_{22}), \quad R_{L2} = \text{real}(Z_{22}) \quad (11)$$

Then, the coupling factor can be expressed as [22]:

$$k_{12} k_{21} = \frac{\text{imag}(Z_{21})}{\text{imag}(Z_{11}) \text{imag}(Z_{22})} \quad (12)$$

Thus, combining equations (3) and (12), the total coupling of the TX and RX coils with the body can be obtained from the experimental Z-parameters considering $k_{12} k_{21} = kb_{TX} kb_{RX}$.

On the other hand, an alternative path to couple the TX with the RX is through the air, as shown in Fig. 13. In this case, the T-model becomes symmetrical, and the coupling coefficient (k_a) can be considered linear. Then, the equation (3) can be rewritten as:

$$k_a = \frac{M_x}{\sqrt{L_{TX} L_{RX}}} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 13 Components of the HBC coupling factor. (Here, L_B represents the body's effective longitudinal and transversal inductive effects).

Then, for MHBC, the total coupling factor (k_{HBC}) comprises the contributions of the coupling through the air, k_a , and the coupling through the body ($k_b = kb_{TX} kb_{RX}$). Thus, the total coupling can be described as the superposition of k_a and k_b and expressed by:

$$k_{HBC} = k_b \pm k_a \quad (14)$$

Notice that the linear contribution of k_a becomes to act as an offset for the k_{HBC} . Therefore, it is necessary for a procedure to identify and remove its effects from the total coupling and after that, to get the actual coupling of the inductors with the body. In the following section, a proposed method is explained.

A. Experimental determination of the coupling paths for MHBC.

To determine the influence of the coupling through the air path, S-parameters were performed from 1 MHz up to 20 MHz. Using solenoid and planar coils in two scenarios: *i*) keeping the inductors in the air, as shown in Fig. 14 a) – b); and *ii*) placing them on the human body, as shown in Fig. 14 c) – d). In all cases, the reference impedance for VNA was established using a SOLT (short-open-load-thru) calibration procedure.

Fig. 14. Experimental setup for determining the coupling factor through the air using a) planar inductors and b) solenoids. Test setup for determining the HBC coupling factor using c) planar inductors and d) solenoids.

According to the experimental results, the solenoid coil shows a higher k factor than the planar coil in the air because solenoids are set up to be faced, favoring the perpendicular flow of the magnetic field. On the other hand, when the body is near k is higher when planar inductors are used, increasing the signal level between transmitter and receiver, even as the channel length increases. Thus, comparatively, the k factor increases significantly when the planar inductors are used to excite the signal into the body, as shown in Fig. 15 a) and b). Then, the planar inductor could be a better option to couple signals into the human body.

Fig. 15. Comparison of the k factor for a) solenoids and b) planar inductors, when they are in the air (k_a) or when the body is near (k_{HBC}).

Once the k_{HBC} and k_a factors are achieved, the coupling through the body can be determined from (14). In this case, k_b values were obtained for both planar and solenoid coils, as shown in Fig. 16.

Fig. 16. Comparison for k_b factor for solenoids and planar inductors.

Finally, mutual inductance between Tx and Rx when the body is near (M_X); between Tx and body (M_{TX}); and between body and Rx (M_{RX}) can be obtained from [18]:

$$M_X = k_a \sqrt{L_{TX} L_{RX}} \quad (15)$$

$$M_{TX} = k_b (L_{TX} L_B) \quad (16)$$

$$M_{RX} = k_b (L_{RX} L_B) \quad (17)$$

B. Efficiency computation

Efficiency (η) in the near field, defined as the transfer of electrical energy through electromagnetic induction between Tx and Rx coils, can be computed conventionally from S-parameters as [27]:

$$\eta = \frac{|S_{21}|^2}{1 - |S_{11}|^2} \times 100 \quad (18)$$

The results when equation (18) is used are shown in Fig. 17. Note that η is bigger for planar inductors than solenoids and increases as channel length. It is consistent with the fact that the reflection coefficient for solenoids increases with channel length due to a reduction in transmission. Additionally, considering that the surrounding environment does not significantly influence MHBC

[28], different scenarios must not change significantly $\Delta\eta$, evidencing a better performance when planar inductors are used.

Fig. 17. Efficiency comparison for solenoids and planar inductors.

V. EQUIVALENT CIRCUIT MODEL FOR MHBC AND EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

Using planar inductors for stimulating the signal into the body, these inductors a biophysical-based equivalent circuit model is proposed in this section. This model is consistent with the equivalent circuit for human tissues shown in Fig. 7. It includes longitudinal and transversal effects from tissues and the mutual coupling between external inductors with the human body, M_{TX} and M_{RX} . Additionally, it consists of the environment coupling between transmitter and receiver inductors, as shown in Fig. 18.

Fig. 18. Proposed equivalent circuit model for MHBC.

Consistently, L_{RX} , L_{TX} , M_X , M_{TX} , and M_{RX} values were obtained directly from measurements, using equations (9), (11), (15)-(17). Also, an optimization procedure using Advanced Design System (ADS) from Keysight [29] was performed to identify the longitudinal and transversal contributions to L_B , i.e., L_L and L_T . Starting values to determine the actual L_B were obtained from [28]. Then, the optimization was performed using the Optim tool provided by ADS, establishing a random search with 100 iterations to minimize the residuals and the desired error of less than 0.01%.

As shown in Fig. 19 (a, b, and c), the longitudinal parameters (R_L , L_L , and C_L) rise as the channel length increases; it could be attributed to the fact that when the channel becomes longer, the impedance becomes higher. In contrast, transversal parameters (R_T , L_T , and C_T) become relatively constant, suggesting that the signal is confined in the skin due to its predominant dielectric behavior. Thus, the variation of the parameters constituting the

proposed model indicates that the transmission is established by the excitation waveguide modes confined in the skin layers.

Notice in Fig. 19(d) that the mutual inductance (M_{TX}) remains almost constant on the transmitter side; it could be because the TX coil doesn't change, then kb_{TX} , which describes the relation between L_{TX} and L_B , remains almost constant. On the other hand, as the signal propagates along the channel, it attenuates, causing a reduction of flux from the body to the receiver coil. So, on the receiver side, the kb_{RX} decreases, as well as the mutual inductance on the receiver side (M_{RX}) decreases too. In the same way, M_X has slight variations because, in this case, the communication is established through the air, and the surrounding conditions don't impact the mutual behavior between the LTX and LRX appreciably.

Fig. 19. Dependence of the constitutive parameters of the model on the length of the channel.

Finally, circuit simulations were performed for different channel lengths to validate the proposed model. Fig. 20 shows that a good correlation experiment-simulation from 1 to 20 MHz was obtained for all analyzed cases. At this point, it is important to mention that, following [30]–[32], no significant pathloss variations are expected for different subjects.

Fig. 20. Experiment-simulation correlation for different MHBC channel lengths.

VI. MHBC POTENTIALS FOR NEAR FIELD COMMUNICATION

HBC uses the human body as a transmission medium; due that the body could become a kind of antenna, users do not need to

mind the size and the place of the device's antenna. Then, it is expected to realize a natural and intuitive user interface by HBC. On the other hand, Near Field Communication (NFC) is a short-range wireless technology that allows data exchange between two devices in proximity (~10 cm) to each other without contact, usually at a frequency of 13.56 MHz [33].

NFC technology works on the principle of mutual induction between the receiver and the transmitter and becomes compatible technology with MHBC for devices operating in proximity to each other or the human skin. However, as discussed previously, in the case of MHBC, designing practical products for interaction with NFC devices is preferable to designing planar coils that induce a longitudinal E-field to increase the antenna effect for the body. According to EM simulations, the range operation for NFC devices operating around the body is less than 60 mm when a planar inductor is used as a transmitter. As shown in Fig. 21. Notice also that using solenoids as a transmitter, the E-field near the body decreases sharply when moving away, restricting the possibility of operating NFC at less than 10 mm from the skin.

Fig. 21. E-field strength outside the body for MHBC using (a) planar inductor and (b) solenoids.

If well, planar coils offer better characteristics to induce electric signals into the body and could be better for interaction with external devices. The radiated field imposes a challenge regarding security because more complexity in encryption of the information is required.

Regarding bandwidth, HBC can give BW of approximately 10 MHz [34], [35]. The main limitation on the bandwidth of HBC arises from the skin's lower conductivity, which drastically decreases that bandwidth. However, potential applications in interactive systems, gaming, smart keys, HBC-RFID systems, and body sensor networks have been explored recently [36]–[38]. However, an open research issue is the powering of HBC devices interacting with NFC or RFIDs; in this regard, works like [39], [40] propose harvesting techniques to collect energy, while works like [41] introduce a new concept to transfer power via human skin to enable wireless, battery-less wearable devices called *SkinnyPower*. In essence, it uses the body to transmit the information signal and power simultaneously the HBC devices connected to the body capacitively.

The main advantage of the HBC over other Body Area Network (BAN) technologies, like NFC, is that to reach similar data rates (<100 kbps), NFC consumes approximately 130 μ W/bit. In contrast, HCB consumes <10 nJ/bit [42], [43], showing the huge potential for HBC for ultra-low power-hungry transceivers and opening the possibility to take advantage of the radiated fields near the skin when the correct excitation is implemented, as was shown along this work.

VII. CONCLUSION

MHBC shows a huge potential for application in fully portable systems, avoiding the necessity of attaching electrodes to the skin. Our experimental results show that planar inductors are more suitable for implementing practical applications than coils. This can be explained by the fact that planar inductors can be maintained closer than coil inductors, which produce a current flowing longitudinally and intensifying the EM interaction with the human channel, which simultaneously takes advantage of the electro and magneto quasi-static fields. Besides, the current induced for the planar inductor is longitudinal through the human body, making the coupling factor better than the coil when channel length increases.

A biophysical analysis validates the proposed equivalent circuit model, verified by experimental results. It provides an excellent experiment-simulation fit up to 20 MHz for all channel length measurements, which is a helpful tool for design purposes.

In this paper, for the first time, an analysis through simulation and experiments was performed to fundamentally understand the strengths and limitations of the MHBC channel, its limitations, and probabilities for implementing practical applications of MHBC together with other BAN technologies like NFC. And finally, operational limits for the interaction with external devices were established according to the orientation and geometry of the transmitter and receiver coils.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank anonymous reviewers for their insightful comments.

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